

**POLITICOPHOBIA AND VOTING BEHAVIOUR AMONG OBAFEMI AWOLOWO
UNIVERSITY STUDENTS**

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CERTIFICATION

I hereby certify that this project was carried out by **AMUSAN DARE VICTOR** with matriculation number; **ASE/2015/113** of the Department of Arts and Social Science, Faculty of Education, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State in fulfillment for the award of Bachelor of Education (B.Ed) in Political Science under my supervision.

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DEDICATION

This essay was dedicated to almighty God, the Alpha and Omega, The Author and the finisher of my faith, for his infinite mercy and abundant grace over my life towards the success of this research work.

I also dedicate this essay to my parents Chief Mr. and Mrs. F. L. Amusan (JP) for their support towards the success of this academic race.

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ABSTRACT

The study is on Politicophobia and voting behaviour among Obafemi Awolowo University Students. The total populations of 140 students were selected in all thirteen (13) faculties in Obafemi Awolowo University. The researcher used questionnaires as the instrument for the data collection. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. A total of 129 respondents made undergraduate students while 11 postgraduate respondents were used for the study. The data collected were presented and analyzed using simple percentage and frequencies.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Fear is a feeling experienced at danger sight or threat that occurs in certain types of organisms, which causes a huge change in metabolic and organ functions and eventually causes a change in behavior, such as hiding, crying and fleeing from some events.

Fear is a feeling induced by perceived danger or threat that occurs in certain types of organisms, which causes a change in metabolic and organ functions and ultimately a change in behavior, such as fleeing, hiding, or freezing from perceived traumatic events. Fear in human beings can occur in response to a certain stimulus occurring in the present, or in anticipation or expectation of a future threat perceived as a risk to body or life. The fear response arises from the perception of danger leading to a confrontation with or escapes from extreme cases of fear i.e horror and terror can be a freeze response or paralysis. In humans and animals, fear is modulated by the process of cognition and learning. Also, fear is perceived as rational and irrational. Rational fear is a fear of something that presents clear and present danger while an irrational fear of something unlikely to cause harm.

Politophobia among undergraduate students is a prevailing issue that has affected the level at which students involve in voting process and political processes as a whole in Students' government in various educational institution. Politophobia, or fear of politics, is a catch all term that encompasses a wide range of individual fears. While there is limited research on Politophobia, it is real and experienced by many. Some people are afraid of the political process, others of politicians. Some fear going to a polling location and casting voting a vote, while still others are afraid of the responsibility of choosing elected officials. Because there are so many variations on the Politophobia, the fear is extremely

individualized. This research looks at the voting behavior aspect of the term Politicophobia among Obafemi Awolowo University Undergraduate Students, Ile-ife.

Students get less involved with political activities which include contesting for election and voting process. The low level of political participation among students evolve as a result of less effective political socialization that exists in the society, the act of transmitting political orientation and behavioral pattern to young people, emigrants or new members of the society has been unsuccessful which eventually reflect on youths who are undergraduate students.

Furthermore, looking at the different levels of political socialization from childhood to Adolescent stage in which youths from childhood who took some decision which results in a great consequential outcome will be fearful to make some decisions which might include political participation due to the failure of Adults in the society of successfully transmit/transfer the political norms and values to them during their adolescent/youthful stage to awaken their desire to get themselves involved in Political processes.

Politics is a set of activities associated with the governance of a country or an area. It involves making decisions that apply to a group of members. It refers to achieving and exercising positions of governance organized control over a human community, particularly a state. The governing process of a state is also called the act of politics in which the responsibility of upholding the sovereignty of any state or society is monitored, administered and executed by a group of individuals.

Voting is a method administered in a group, such as multi-personnel gathering, to make a collective decision and also to express an opinion usually after discussions, debates or campaigns. Voting is also a choice made by either a person or group on an occasion to express his/her decision. It is also referring to as the act of indicating one's choice

Voting behavior is a form of electoral behavior. Voting behavior pertains to the actions or inactions of citizens in respect of participating in the elections that take place for members of their local, regional, or national governments. The behavior results either in support for political candidates or parties or abstention from the voting process. Trends in voting or abstention from voting has demonstrable statistical relationships with the socioeconomic characteristics of an electorate and the spatial context within which its political socialization has occurred. Among these are levels of income, age group, ethnicity, religious affiliation or beliefs, urbanization, and region.

1.2 Statement of the Problems

Despite the longstanding concern over youth turnout along with obvious reasons to think that students differ from other young adults, there is almost no theoretical or empirical work specifically devoted to college students. Many students will vote later in life, but the lack of knowledge about their turnout behavior while in college, still forming their political orientation.

Most undergraduate students always find themselves are in a confusing state to engage in a major self decision action because, many often for the first time in their lives, are moving away from their home life and parents who happened to be a major stakeholder in their previous decisions. They often find themselves in a situation unlike any they will face in later years living in close quarters with a set of same-age individuals who are also undergraduate students with very different career interests. Many are also in the unique situation of having a choice about where to vote, most are sometimes confused about whether to register for voting in their hometown or their college.

However, Politicophobia among undergraduate students has effects on their voting behavior ranging from; political apathy, low turnout during election, fear of politicians,

wrong decision making, Confusion, frustration and oppression from society which results into; Inaccurate reflection of the will of the people during elections, unequal representation among various parts of the population, lack of Proper orientation about the political process of the larger society after their period as an undergraduate student, higher opportunity for vote-rigging, apartheid feeling for political processes. It is on this note that this study is designed to investigate the effect "politico phobia" among undergraduate students has on the "voting behavior".

1.3 Objective of the Study

This research is essentially designed to:

1. investigate the level of political participation of students
2. identify the various factors responsible for fear of political participation among undergraduate students.
3. examine the perception of political involvement
4. find out students' view about voting
5. suggest ways by which political orientation/ participation of students can be awakened

1.4 Research Questions

In an attempt to carry out a thorough investigation of the effect of Politico phobia among undergraduate students, it is very significant and essential to ask the following questions.

- What are the levels of political participation among OAU undergraduate students?
- What factors are responsible for political apathy among OAU undergraduate students?

- What is the perception of OAU students on Electoral processes?
- What are the possible ways of orientating students' on how to actively participate in the voting/political process?

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study focuses on politicophobia and voting behavior of Undergraduate Students' in Obafemi Awolowo University. Most students on Campus have apartheid feelings towards political processes going on around them, different Students' Associations engage in campaigns, manifesto, Political Debates and so on, but it is observed that most students involved have one or two reasons to believe that engaging in politics/electoral processes on campus is not necessary but rather prefer to focus in their studies.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The is to be carried out on undergraduate students in all faculties across on Obafemi Awolowo University to Specifically cover how politicophobia affects the voting behavior of undergraduate students

1.7 Operational Definition of Terms

- **POLITICOPHOBIA:** The fear of getting involved in political processes
- **VOTING:** Voting is a method for a group, such as a meeting or an electorate, to make a collective decision or express an opinion usually following discussions, debates or election campaigns
- **BEHAVIOR:** how one acts or conducts oneself, especially towards others
- **VOTING BEHAVIOUR:** Voting behavior is the way that different people tend to vote

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

The review of related literature is given under the following sub-headings:

- 2.0 Conceptual framework
- 2.1 The Concept Politics
- 2.2 Different Level of Politics
- 2.3 The Concept Fear
- 2.4 Forms of Fear
- 2.5 The Concept Voting Behavior
- 2.6 Causes of Politicophobia in Nigeria
- 2.7 Effect of Politicophobia on Political processes
- 2.8 Impact of Politicophobia on Politics
- 2.9 Politicophobia effect on voting trends since 1999 and the rhythm of Politicophobia
- 2.9 Conceptual linkages between politicophobia and the voting patterns that affect Nigeria political system

2.0 Conceptual framework

Politophobia fear of politics is another factor that affect the active participation of citizens or electorate in political processes which includes contesting and voting acts. This implies that the degree at which members of a particular society generates the fear of involving in political processes determines the state of such society in selecting leaders and governing processes. The implication of this is that any society whose citizens have the fear of engaging in political processes will eventually end up having non compelling voting behavior in electoral processes of constituting a government to manage the available resources in the society. However, it is expedient that both young and old citizens of any society engage in any political processes i.e. voting in such society

Moreso, Politophobia among undergraduate students is a prevailing issue that has affected the level at which students involve in voting process and political processes as a whole in Students' government in various educational institution. Therefore, it is expected of students or electorates in a particular society engage in political processes to the best of their ability in order to bring good and desired results in their political activities.

Before going further, it is pertinent to explain thoroughly on the concept Politics and the different levels it exists, concept of fear and it various forms, concept of voting and it various process of voting.

2.1 The Concept Politics

Politics is a set of activities associated with the governance of a country or an area. It involves making decisions that apply to a group of members. It refers to achieving and exercising positions of governance organized control over a human community, particularly a state. The governing process of a state is also called the act of politics in which the

responsibility of upholding the sovereignty of any state or society is monitored, administered and executed by a group of individuals.

After the behavioral revolution, political scientists have replaced 'state' by 'political system,' considering the former as formal, inadequate and unsatisfactory. Still it is not clear which is the central element of political system. Classical political thinkers had found knowledge, reason, natural law, religion or conventional law as the basic element of state. Most of the modern political scientists find 'legitimate physical compulsion' as the key variable of political system. For Easton, it is 'authoritative allocation of values for society'.

Lasswell and Kaplan (1950) regard 'severe deprivations' as the basic material of political system. Dahl relates it to power, government and authority. Catlin discovers 'control over wills' as the basis. Almond defines the political system, more or less, as 'the legitimate, order-maintaining or transforming system in the society'. All the scholars have called its various organs and processes in varying terms.

Easton (1965) has put them in the two broad categories of 'inputs' and 'outputs'. A 'political system' cannot be physically separated from its non-political aspects, and is, therefore, usually understood and studied in an analytical or conceptual manner. Society as a whole makes up the general social system, which contains many subsystems.

Political system is one of these subsystems. When the political system is to be studied as a whole along with its intra-subsystems, then, it is treated as a 'system'. Besides that, 'system' can be considered as a part of environment. Thus, the concept of 'system' both in interlocking micro and macro forms, saves us from the error of considering 'systems' as isolated, separate, or independent entities. Besides throwing light on their interconnections, one can examine their discrete nature, and separate empirical existence.

According to Almond (1966), the political system in a society, is 'legitimate, order maintaining' or trans-forming system, Wiseman maintains that every political system involves political structures, actors, or roles performed by their agents, patterns of interaction existing between individuals or collectivities, and political processes. In the 'political system' of Kaplan also, there are recognizable multivariate interests. Instead of always being opposite, sometimes they are complementary to each other. There are regular structures and channels to reach the decisions and judgments related to particular interests. General rules are prescribed to govern the actors and activities relating to particular decisions and judgments.

Principal elements in politics

A political system, according to Michels, has the following features:

- a. It is a permanent entity, existing amidst a broader environment and includes many other units.
- b. It consists of an identifiable and measurable set of interdependent elements or variables.
- c. It has boundaries which keep it separate from general environment.
- d. It is constituted around certain problems, objectives or goals, and builds up certain structures.
- e. Along with increase of specific problems and evolution of goals, it develops specific structures and processes, leading to more and more differentiation.

However, political scientists, sociologists, and political sociologists have analysed political systems with varying frames of references and different goals. More important among them are Talcott Parsons, David Easton, Gabriel Almond, and Morton Kaplan.

Perspectives of Parsons and Easton are more conceptual. Almond and Kaplan have gone towards empirical research and theory making. Thus, there are many variations among them. Before we discuss it in detail, 'General Systems' would be taken up first.

2.2 Different level of Politics

Formal politics refers to the operation of a constitutional system of government and publicly defined institutions and procedures. Political parties, public policy or discussions about war and foreign affairs would fall under the category of Formal Politics. Many people view formal politics as something outside of themselves, but that can still affect their daily lives.

Semi-formal politics is politics in government associations such as neighborhood associations, or student governments where student government political party politics is often important.

Informal politics is understood as forming alliances, exercising power and protecting and advancing particular ideas or goals. Generally, this includes anything affecting one's daily life, such as the way an office or household is managed, or how one person or group exercises influence over another. Informal Politics is typically understood as everyday politics, hence the idea that "politics is everywhere".

2.3 The Concept of Fear

Fear is a feeling induced by perceived danger or threat that occurs in certain types of organisms, which causes a change in metabolic and organ functions and ultimately a change in behavior, such as fleeing, hiding, or freezing from perceived traumatic events. Fear in human beings can occur in response to a certain stimulus occurring in the present, or in anticipation or expectation of a future threat perceived as a risk to body or life. The fear response arises from the perception of danger leading to a confrontation with or escapes from

extreme cases of fear i.e horror and terror can be a freeze response or paralysis. In humans and animals, fear is modulated by the process of cognition and learning. Also, fear is perceived as rational and irrational. Rational fear is a fear of something that presents clear and present danger while an irrational fear of something unlikely to cause harm. Not surprisingly, fear is presented very differently across fields within the academic, peer-reviewed literature. Yet even within scholarship, there is significant disparity across definitions. Kish-Gephart and colleagues (2009), in one of the few articles on fear's influence in the workplace in the organizational sciences, provide an excellent technical overview of some potential origins of fear and an understanding of the role of fear in organizational silence, yet they do not define a specific construct of fear. Rather, they describe fear as a "powerful emotion that shapes many aspects of our lives" (p. 164). For the purpose of studying the climate of fear, Ashkanasy and Nicholson (2003) adopt a broad definition of fear to be "a generalised [sic] experience of apprehension in the workplace" (p. 24). Within the biological sciences, fear is more specifically defined. For example, one study defines fear as, "a sufficiently potent, biologically driven, motivated state wherein a single, salient threat guides behavior" (Bay & Algase, 1999, p. 105). In the psychological sciences, fear is defined as, "a reaction to an external stimulus...and appears to be associated with autonomic hyperarousal when the individual is exposed to the stimulus...a common adaptive response to an immediate, threatening situation" (Pavuluri, Henry, & Allen, 2002, p. 273). For the purpose of developing his widely-cited Fear Survey Schedule-II in the field of psychology, Geer (1965) considers fear to be "a negative emotional response evoked by a relatively specific stimulus" (p.45). Fear has been defined at a state level (Bay & Algase, 1999; Pavuluri et al., 2002); that is, it is a response to a "single salient threat" (Bay & Algase, 1999, p. 106) that might include a sudden change in environment, a negative facial expression, or some other event in which a threat is perceived as imminent. Others have focused on a more dispositional

form of fear (e.g., Knaus, 2008; Lerner & Keltner, 2001). Lerner and Keltner (2001) distinguish dispositional or trait affect from an emotional state by indicating, “emotions trigger changes in cognition, physiology, and action that, although tailored to help the individual respond to the event that evoked the emotion, often persist beyond the eliciting situation”. Taking this even further, Knaus (2008) refers to these types of persistent fears as ‘parasitic fears’ that stimulate “false alerts of fictional dangers”

2.4 Forms of Fear

Fear of the Political Process: Election season is generally filled with mudslinging, pointed advertisements, and hard-fought debates. If you are uncomfortable with conflict, you might be tempted to hide in the house with the television off during the months preceding a major election.

Fear of Politicians: Like lawyers and used-car salesmen, politicians have a reputation for being slick and untrustworthy. While many people actively dislike politicians, actual fear of them is somewhat more unusual. What is more common, however, is the fear of a specific politician.

During election season, it seems that the entire country takes sides. From major corporations to individual religious leaders, politicians seek out endorsements that they feel can help their bid for election. But almost invariably, endorsing one candidate means speaking out against his or her opponents. When that message comes from a trusted source, it is easy to take it to heart. You may begin to fear a politician who is running ahead in the polls and happens to be someone against whom your pastor, closest friend or boss is spreading a message of hatred.

Fear of Casting a Vote: Polling locations can be intimidating, particularly to those with social phobia, agoraphobia or claustrophobia. Although most districts now have laws

preventing campaigning within the polling place, supporters for both sides often line the sidewalks in a last-minute bid to convince voters to choose a specific candidate. It can feel something like walking the gauntlet as campaigners shout slogans and distribute literature.

Inside the polling location, you must go through a series of steps from presenting identification to casting your vote. Poll workers are eager to demonstrate sample ballots and ensure that you understand the process. For those who suffer from certain types of social phobia or agoraphobia, this interaction can feel agonizing.

Fear of Choosing Elected Officials: Although each person holds only one vote, that vote can make a critical difference in the ultimate outcome of the election. If you are unsure where you stand on the issues, unfamiliar with some of the candidates or unclear on how to fill out the ballot, you may be afraid of making the wrong choice. The fear of responsibility is powerful, and some people develop a nearly paralyzing fear of negatively impacting the future.

Fear of Election Results: Some people are unafraid of casting a vote but are fearful of the direction in which the country is heading. This appears to be especially true when elections happen to fall during a period of war, economic uncertainty or other negativity. Campaign promises, attack ads, and mudslinging heighten the effects, with each side trying desperately to convince voters that "bad things" will happen if the other side is elected.

During presidential elections, the balance of power is frequently mentioned. Legislation must pass through the House and the Senate before being signed by the president. Controlling two or even all three branches of government makes it easier for a political party to pass its agenda, so naturally, both major parties want to gain as much control as possible. But this fight for control makes it easy for those who support the "losing" side to develop strong fears of what the future will hold.

2.5 The Concept Voting Behavior

Voting is a method administered in a group, such as multi-personnel gathering, to make a collective decision and also to express an opinion usually after discussions, debates or campaigns. Voting is also a choice made by either a person or group on an occasion to express his/her decision. It is also referring to as the act of indicating one's choice.

The theoretical assumptions models of voting behavior are defined in three essential works: *The People's Choice* (Lazarsfeld, Berelson, & Gaudet, 1944), *Voting* (Berelson, Lazarsfeld, & McPhee, 1954) and *Personal Influence* (Katz & Lazarsfeld, 1955). The research conducted by Lazarsfeld et al. (1944) at Ohio State (Erie County), using questionnaire as a technique of investigation for the first time in the study of a U.S. presidential election — one which opposed Franklin Roosevelt to Wendell Willkie in 1940 — cuts away from the type methodological approach that hitherto characterized the study of voting behavior (Barnes & Kaase, 1979). Paul Lazarsfeld, whose previous interests had focused on the study of the psychological mechanisms involved in the processes of choice and in the effects of publicity, advertising and mass media on consumer behavior had two main objectives in this research: to study the effects of exposure to the media, that is, to know how voters arrive at their decisions and the role of media in this process; and to test a new methodology of successive interviews with a panel of subjects and a control group (Rossi, 1964). The study, whose report was published under the title *The People's Choice* (Lazarsfeld, Berelson, & Gaudet, 1944), begins by characterizing the supporters of the two main political parties in the U.S. using a panel of 600 subjects who were interviewed seven times over the seven months of campaign, to then identify the voters who changed their position during the campaign period, comparing three groups: those who decided their vote before beginning the campaign, those whose decision was taken during the party convention and those that decided their vote only at an advanced stage of the campaign. The central

hypothesis of Lazarsfeld et al. (1944) was that the act of voting is an individual act, affected mainly by the personality of the voter and his exposure to the media. The results, however, contradict the main thesis, suggesting that the effect of the media in electoral decision was minimal and that the decisive influence was the social groups to which they belonged. In the final two chapters of his book — “The Political homogeneity of Social Groups” and “The Nature of Personal Influence” — the focus is exactly on the theoretical elaboration of these conclusions, which are presented as revealed by news research: “The significance of this area of political behavior was highlighted by the study but further investigation is necessary to establish it more firmly” (Lazarsfeld et al., 1968, p. 69).

However, the three main propositions on voting behaviour in Nigeria were identified to have included Sociological Approach; party identification model and rational choice. The sociological model emphasize on voting behaviour as a result of impact of social structure suggesting that social group membership influence voting behaviour. This is visible in Nigerian context where belonging to a religious group or ethnic group or certain geographical area determines voters’

Behaviour in an election. Belonging to a particular social group automatically qualifies a candidate to receive votes of such members of that group.

The party identification approach is a situation where partisanship is highly stable over time. Here, voters are less likely to make distinctions between their vote choice and partisan dispositions. This situation is also applicable within Nigerian context where some sections of the population became attached to a given political party irrespective of the candidate as a result of their partisan position towards that particular party.

The rational choice approach lays much emphasis on voters’ choice of their candidates in an election based on issues and policy design of the political parties. The choice

here is rational. This situation, however, is not obtainable in Nigerian system except to a smaller extent and even this one; is found among elites who chose their party or candidates due to the economic or political benefits they will gain from voting such candidates. But, common voter in Nigerian democracy has no rationality in choice as they tend to vote according to sentiments.

The role played by ethnicity and religion in democratization process in Nigeria is harmful to the system. Mimiko (2006) argued that, the tremendous effects of ethnic and religious crises faced by Nigeria in the current phase of democratization are the outcome of the elite's manipulation of ethnic and religious identity. This has been associated with the problems of historical configuration of the country, the nature of political class and the manner in which they struggle.

This has led to an exclusive nature of the politics of ethnic and religious identity among different groups in the country. This has affected the political behaviour of the electorates to align themselves with ethnic and religious political parties. This in return affects voting pattern during any elections whether Presidential or Gubernatorial.

2.6 Cause of Politicophobia among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria

1. Fear of being victimized
2. No Orientation towards political processes
3. Religious Beliefs
4. Unreliable Results in Elections
5. Political corruptions
6. Election Violence and Death Threats

2.7 Effect of Politicophobia on Political Processes

Politicophobia has always been a cultural and historical problem in politics. In addition, many citizens whose wish to nurture their political behaviour one way or the other ends up giving it up because of the various historical reports about political processes.

Inaccurate reflection of the will of the people during elections: Most political processes or election results are not always in favor of the electorate because most electorate who decided to stay apartheid opinion did not count in the political process meanwhile those who have decided to vote or engage in the political process might not vote or act in favor of the apartheid which later usually resolve into demonstration like protest, road blockage, and the like.

Less representation of masses in government: Majority of the masses are prone not to be less represented in government because most citizens have apartheid themselves from politics which in return might deprive them of governmental benefits because there is no solicitor for them in government. Most areas where there is low orientation or no involvement in political processes are likely to benefit less form the government because there is no voice to speak for them in government which in return might subject them to remain in poverty and less developed.

Lack of Proper orientation about the political process of the larger society after their period as an undergraduate student: Most undergraduate students after leaving tertiary institution are likely to find themselves at dead end at when where and how to fit themselves into formal contemporary societal politics because of low or now orientation about semi-formal politics in schools where they can build their profile or career. Most graduates who did not engage in political process in their undergraduate days finds it difficult to move far in

formal politics in the society because they are not familiar with the political culture and trends.

Higher opportunity for vote-rigging: Vote rigging is highly practicable where there is low turnout from electorate to engage in political processes because the void left can be used to turn the process in favor of any candidate who rigging is aimed for. E.g. It is claimed by various electoral observers that vote rigging takes place mostly in Northern part of Nigeria because most electorate over have no orientation about the voting processes and therefore abstain from voting processes in which gives room for electoral officers to perform electoral malpractices.

Apartheid feeling for political processes: Most students who have not been familiar with political processes because of the fear of politics mostly do abstain from political processes afterwards because of the perception they have about politics.

Also less experienced eligible voter's tests relationships among cynicism toward the political system, negativism toward campaigns, apathy toward political participation, third-person perceptions for political polling and advertising, voting efficacy and voting intentions. Although Cynicism has both negative and positive associations with voting efficacy. Apathy is related to reduce voting efficacy, with efficacy positively associated with voting intentions. It is concluded that negative feelings like fear and Apathy towards politics dampen, young voters' intent to participate in the elective process. It appears that the voters who do not have believe in politicians or have the feeling of not fulfilling promises are likely not to participation in elections

2.8 Politicophobia effect on voting trends since 1999 and the rhythm of Politicophobia

Nigeria has witnessed five general elections conducted by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) since the return to civil rule in 1999. Each of the successive elections has had areas of commendation and areas that need to be improved upon. The fourth republic has been the longest uninterrupted period of democratic governance in Nigeria since independence in 1960 and the founding of the republic in 1963. The successful transition – from ruling parties being perpetually in power to political alternation of power from a ruling to an opposition party – which occurred in 2015, is a sign of growing consolidation of democracy. As critical democracy stakeholders continue to engage the political process, the country’s democratic culture is deepening and the quality and level of citizens’ participation in governance continues to grow.

From the transition elections of 1999, Nigeria generated a voter register with 57.9 million registered voters, out of an estimated population of 119,327,100. This meant that 48.5% of the population registered to vote in 1999. By 2003, the percentage of the population that registered to vote decreased to 45.7%. This trend continued in 2007 when the number of registered voters as a percentage of total population further decreased to 41.9%. The trend changed slightly in 2011 when the number of registered voters as a percentage of total population increased to 45.1%. However, the progress witnessed in 2011 was reversed in 2015 when the number of registered voters as a percentage of total population dropped drastically to 38.3%. Currently, the trend of voter registration has returned to the path of increase as the number of registered voters as a percentage of the total population has increased to 84.0 million representing 42.8% of the total population. When compared with the situation twenty years ago, the number of registered voters as a percentage of total

population has declined 5.7% while the number of registered voters measured in absolute numbers has increased by 26,065,139, representing a 44.9% increase.

Generally, the trend in the number of registered voters as a percentage of total population for the past twenty years has been that of retrogression. One reason for this decline in the number of registered voters as a percentage of the total population could be due to dissatisfaction and disenchantment of voters with the political system, after democratic rule failed to deliver the benefits associated with democracy such as improved living standards. The high rate of electoral violence experienced in various phases of elections in previous years could be another reason for the decline in voter registration. Again, the integrity of the elections conducted, particularly that of 2003 and 2007, are considered among the worst elections in the fourth republic. This may have also undermined voters' confidence in the electoral processes and reduced their participation in elections. More so, the clean-up of voter's register and the introduction of permanent voters cards (PVC) involving biometric capture of voters contributed to the drop in the number of registered voters particularly in 2015 where the number of registered voters dropped to 69.3 million from 73.5 million in 2011.

"Generally, the trend in the number of registered voters as a percentage of total population for the past twenty years has been that of retrogression. One reason for this decline in the number of registered voters as a percentage of the total population could be due to dissatisfaction and disenchantment of voters with the political system, after democratic rule failed to deliver the benefits associated with democracy such as improved living standards." -

INEC

Despite the general decline experienced in the past twenty years, year-on-year analysis reveals that 2011 and 2019 are remarkable for the slight increase obtained over the respective previous years in terms of absolute number of registered voters and number of registered

voters as a percentage of total population. The reason for the increase witnessed in 2011 over the 2007 figure could be due to the electoral reform embarked upon by the new leadership of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), particularly the introduction of biometric voter's register which gradually restored faith in the integrity of the electoral process and increased momentum in voter registration. Interestingly, between 2015 and 2019 alone, the number of registered voters increased by 14.7 million representing 25.4% increase in the number of registered voters over the previous year. This increase may be connected to increase in voter education and mobilization by political parties, civil society groups, INEC and other relevant stakeholders

Generally, the key trends in voter registration over the past twenty years are:

1. Since 1999, voter registration has never reached 50% of the country's total population. This means that less than half of the population registers to vote in elections and decide the leadership that emerges.
2. The average percentage of registered voters compared to the country's population for the past twenty years is 43.7%.
3. The highest number of registered voters as a percentage of the total population was recorded in 1999 and the lowest was in 2015.
4. While in 2019 the number of registered voters compared to 1999 has increased by 26.1 million or 44.9%, the country's population within the same period increased by 76.6 million or 64.2%. This indicates that the increase in registered voters is not proportional to the increase in the country's population over the twenty year period.

Voters Turnout

Since the return to civil rule in 1999, the 2015 general elections recorded the lowest rate of voter turnout at 29.4 million voters, representing 42.4% of registered voters for the year 2015. This suggests that high voter registration may not automatically translate to increased voter participation in the election. In fact, when examined against the backdrop of voter participation in the three key phases of the election cycle (pre-election, election and post-election), what it means is that the level of participation may be high during the pre-election period measured by voter registration, but participation may be low during the voting period measured by voter turnout.

The long term (1999 – 2015) trend in voter turnout has been that of decline. This reflects the trend in voter registration since the return to civil rule in Nigeria. For instance, the data reveals that voter turnout dropped from 30.2 million or 52.3% of registered voters in 1999 to 29.4 million or 43.7% of registered voters in 2015. Although there was a sharp increase in voter turnout in 2003, this declined again in 2007. This sharp increase in 2003 could be attributed to the tenacious effort by the then president Olusegun Obasanjo to secure a second tenure in office.

In the short term (2011- 2015), there was a significant drop in the voter turnout, from 40.7 million or 55.4% of registered voters in 2011 to 29.4 million or 43.7% in 2015. This is a reflection of the decline in voter registration within the same period where the number of registered voters dropped from 73.5 million or 45.1% of total population in 2011 to 69.3 million or 38.3% of total population in 2015. Moreover, the 2011 general election which witnessed the highest voter registration also experienced a very high (57.4 %) of voter turnout. During the fourth republic this has only been surpassed by the 2007 turnout.

The implication of this trend is that the voter turnout rate has dropped both in the long term (1999 – 2015) and short term (2011 – 2015). The reason for the long-term decline could be the growing disenchantment of the people following the inability of the government to improve livelihoods. It is also possible that the decline is due to the introduction of PVCs. These reduced the incidence of electoral malfeasance such as ballot-stuffing, which previously counted as voter turnout.

The short-term decline between 2011 and 2015 could be attributed to the electoral violence experienced in 2011 and the failure of the government to hold to account perpetrators of the electoral violence. This accentuated the fears of voter and fed into voter apathy or poor voter turnout. Other security issues like the Boko Haram insurgency in the North East may have equally contributed to the decline in voter turnout.

"The short-term decline between 2011 and 2015 could be attributed to the electoral violence experienced in 2011 and the failure of the government to hold to account perpetrators of the electoral violence." - INEC

At several roundtables and workshops, Centre for Democracy and Development (CDD) have found the following as some of the reasons behind voter apathy:

- The absence of dividends of democracy to the people. Many Nigerians, particularly the poor, are yet to feel the impact of transition from military to civil rule in terms of improved welfare and livelihood. This has brought about increased disenchantment with the whole political process as this class of citizens are now in a place where going to the polling unit to vote has lost its meaning.
- The absence of citizens' education, especially for young Nigerians that qualify as first-time-voters. For the first time, some Nigerians have turned 18 years and above

without experiencing military rule. However, on turning 18, most young Nigerians are completely unaware of their civic duties with regards to registering to be able to vote and be voted for in an election. These young Nigerians are not voting because they don't even know the import of such a civic duty.

- The conduct of the political class is unfortunately now becoming a disincentive to some s some politicians say: no matter what; they are going to win. Many voters take that to mean their votes won't count, and so don't participate in elections.
- Insecurity is yet another driver of electoral apathy. Citizens who already feel neglected by government will not be willing to take the risk of going to the polling unit. Several incidences of violence at polling units have been recorded. It is now even common place to see Nigerians of southern extraction leaving the Northern part ahead of every general election for fear of being attacked due to the outcome, and vice versa.

"The 2015 national election was fiercely contested, yet the declining turnout could not be stopped. We considers this a negative trend that could further alienate national leadership from the people." - CDD (Centre for Democracy and Development)

2.9 Conceptual linkages between politicophobia and the voting patterns that affect Nigeria political system

Political behaviour in Nigeria is full of incinerating and abusive language by both the Contestants and the electorates. He cited former President Olusegun Obasanjo in 2007 elections where he said elections is a war and you must win by all means possible. This further interpreted revealed that, in order for the incumbent to win elections, they did not rely on voters' power but through the use of coercive and subjugative method such as political

thuggery, rigging and even political assassination. The electorates are inculcated with such attitude too and it formed a kind of political behaviour among the voters during an election process. Thus, the voting pattern is such in a way that voters are sometimes coerced to vote for a particular candidate or even abandon voting because it will not even count.

Democracy and elections in Nigeria is affected by poor institutionalization of democratic values and culture. Inter-ethnic competition or tribalism is a great weakness which leads to instability in Nigeria's democracy. In addition, constitutional democracy became so fragile in Nigerian state because it was imported. For instance, the Second Republic came to an end as a result of rioting in the Southwest and Southeast that followed the Northern candidate was announced as victorious in the 1984 Presidential election. The military took over immediately. This was as a result of political behaviour and voting culture of the electorates on the perception that only a candidate that emerges from their ethnic or regional or even religious groups can win or rule.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter dealt with the method adopted in gathering information for the study under following headings: Research Design, Population of the study, Sample and sampling techniques, Research instrument, Validity of the instrument, Reliability of the instrument, Administration of the instrument, and method of data analysis.

3.1 Research design

The research design employed for this study was descriptive survey which was in the collection, analysis and interpretation of data to analyses voting behavior and causes of politicophobia among Obafemi Awolowo University Students, Ile-Ife.

3.2 Population of the study

The target population for this research comprised all 13 faculties including postgraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife.

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size for the study comprised 140 students whereby a minimum of 8 students and maximum of 11 students are selected from all 13 faculties and postgraduate college that make up the university. The sample was selected with the use of convenience sampling techniques.

3.4 Research Instrument

The data for the study were collected with the use of designed questionnaire titled, "Politico-phobia and Voting Behavior among Obafemi Awolowo University Students". The questionnaire was made up of three sections viz: A, B, C, D and E

Section A was designed to elicit responses on the personal data of the respondents such as name of Faculty, Sex, Age, Level, Religion and Tribe. This categorization provided an opportunity for a simplified format that would facilitate the analysis of the data

Section B contained information regarding the “level of political participation, with four frequency point modified likers scale ranging from: Often, Sometimes, Rarely and Never

Section C, D and E contained information about “various factors responsible for fear of political participation factors responsible for fear of political participation, perception of political involvement, ad view about voting” respectively with four point modified likers scale ranging from: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree

3.5 Validity of the Instrument

The instrument used for this study was validated by the researcher’s supervisor who ensured that the validity of the instrument was ascertained. The face and content validity of the instrument were established

3.6 Reliability of the Instrument

The method of reliability used for the instrument was test-retest reliability. The instrument was administered on sample of 30 respondents who were not part of the research work, and after about 2 weeks the same instrument was re-administered on the sample of the 60 respondents.

3.7 Administration of the Instrument

The researcher implored the students in the various faculties and post graduate college to supply accurate responses to the questionnaires, and he personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents. In order to ensure good responses and high rate of return of the instrument by the respondents, the researcher explains to the respondents the importance of the study, the confidentiality of their responses and the need for their cooperation in completing the instrument. The researcher waited for the respondents to complete the items in the questionnaire and the questionnaires were retrieved on the spot. A total of one hundred and forty (140) copies of the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents.

3.8 Data Analysis

The researcher made use of simple percentage for the analysis of the data.

CHAPTER FOUR

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Introduction

This Chapter presents the analysis, interpretation and discussion of the data collected from both Undergraduate and post graduates Students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria on Politicophobia and voting behavior Among Obafemi Awolowo University students, Ile-ife. The questionnaire was administered on 140 students and all questionnaires were meaningfully completed. The results are presented as follows

4.2 Data Analysis

Table showing the demographic characteristic of respondents

	Compositions	Frequencies	Percentages
Sex	Male	80	57.1%
	Female	60	42.9%
Age	15-19	40	28.6%
	20-29	87	62.1%
	30-34	13	9.3%
Religion	Christianity	79	56.4%
	Islam	61	43.6%
	Others	0	0%
Tribe	Yoruba	105	75%
	Hausa	1	0.7%
	Igbo	34	16.7%
	Total	140	100%
Level	100	1	0.7%
	200	43	30.7%
	300	43	30.7%
	400	39	27.9%
	500	3	2.1%
	Others	11	7.9%
	Total	140	100%
Faculty	Administration	10	7.1%
	Arts	11	7.9%
	Basic Medical Sciences	9	6.4%
	Education	11	7.9%
	Pharmacy	10	7.1%
	Law	9	8.4%
	Technology	10	7.1%
	Social Sciences	10	7.1%
	Clinical Sciences	8	5.7%
	Agriculture	11	7.9%
	Sciences	10	7.1%
	Post Graduate College	11	7.9%
	Environmental Design and Management	10	7.1%
	Dentistry	10	7.1%
Total	140	100%	

Source: *Field Survey, 2020*

From the survey, 57.1% of the respondents care male and 42.9, the age of the respondents are categorized into three (3) namely: 15- 19, 20-29 and 30-34. Respondents whose age range is between 15 and 19 is 28.6%, 20 and 29 being 62.1 and 30-35 with 9.3% value

Furthermore, the religion of the respondents shows that Christians represented with 56.4 %, Islam with 42.9% with 0.7% missing value. The Tribe of the respondents was also categorized with possible options from Yoruba (75%), Hausa (1.4) and Igbo with (23.6%). The respondents' level shows that 100L students have 0.7%, 200L with 30.7%, 300L with 30.7%, 400L with 27.9%, 500L with 2.1% and others with 7.9%. Lastly, respondents' faculties were also collected. It shows that all the facilities are represented in the study as follows: Administration (7.1%), Arts (7.9%), Agriculture (7.9%), Basic Medical Sciences (6.4%), Clinical Science (5.7%), Dentistry (7.1%), Education (7.9%), Environmental Design and Management (7.1%), Law (6.4), Pharmacy (7.1%), Post Graduate College (7.9%), Science (7.1), Social Science (7.1%) and Technology (7.1%)

Research Question 1: What are the Levels of Political Participation among OAU Students?

Table showing various levels of political participation

S/N	Statement	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
	I do attend political gatherings	28(20%)	51(36.4%)	30(21.4%)	31(22.2%)
	I do vote in elections	39(27.9%)	35(25%)	50(35.7%)	16(11.4%)

Source: *Field Survey, 2020*

The table above shows that 28% of the total respondents often attend political gatherings, 36% acknowledge to sometimes attend political gatherings, 21.4% rarely attend political gatherings and 22.2% were never in attendance of any political gathering. Also From the survey, it could be seen that 27.9 % often and 25% sometimes vote. But those that rarely vote

amount to 35.7% and respondents that never voted is 11.4%. It could be seen that most students still don't participate in the voting process.

We can still acknowledge that quite just simple majority of students' whether most students vote in elections as 52.9 cumulatively often and sometimes choose to vote% while 47.1% of the respondents rarely and never voted.

Hence, from the table and analysis which was done interference can therefore be drawn that although most students claimed to have been attending political gatherings but huge number of them still don't vote in elections.

Table showing the extent sex affects political participation of students of Obafemi Awolowo University.

		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
I do attend Political gatherings	Often	15	12	27
	Sometimes	29	22	51
	Rarely	31	20	51
	Never	4	7	11
	Total	79	61	140

Survey: *Field Survey, 2020*

The table shows that out of 44 out of 79 male respondents sometimes and often attends political gatherings while 34 out of 61 female acts likewise but it could be seen that 36 of male respondents have never or rarely attend political gatherings while 27 of female acts in accordance.

Research question 2: What factors are responsible for political apathy among OAU students?

In order to find out various factors responsible for political apathy among OAU students, Section C of the research questionnaire is directed towards answering this question.

Table showing reasons why students engage in political apathy

S/N	Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	Politics goes along with threats e.g. Death threats and the likes	23(16.4%)	51(36.4%)	50(35.7%)	16(11.4%)
2	Student politicians are always suspended because of their political activities	60(42.9%)	41(29.2%)	32(22.9%)	7(5%)
3	My parents don't want me to engage in politics	13(9.3%)	65(46.4%)	49(35%)	13(9.3)

Source: *Field Survey 2020*

The table shows that the 52.8% response from the respondents agree that politics goes along with threats while the remaining 47.2% disagree and strongly disagree with the statement, most respondents believed that politics is a dangerous game which comes with various threats which might include death and other relative threats although most students agree that politics is always associated with threats but also quite a number of students disagree with this statement which shows that the students are not familiar with culture and nature of politics.

Furthermore, 72.1% of the participants agreed that students who engaged actively in campus politics are always prone to suspension while the 27.9% disagree and strongly disagree with the statement obviously, it can be deduced that one of the reasons why students have apartheid feeling towards political activities on campus is because of the aftermath of engaging in campus politics also most students acknowledge that their parents is also a factor in which 55.7% agree that their parents don't want them to engage in politics while 44.3 disagree and strongly disagree with this.

Research Question3: What is the perception of OAU students' on Electoral process?

Items 1, 3 and 4 in Section D of the questionnaire are directed towards answering the research question.

Table showing students view about political processes

S/N	Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	Voting is the only way to engage in politics	26(18.6%)	40(28.6%)	57(35.7%)	13(17.1%)
2	The appropriate time to engage in politics is during elections	48(34.3%)	29(20.7%)	44(31.4%)	13(13.6%)
3	Voting is enough for me to participate in politics	55(39.3%)	21(15%)	61(43.6%)	3(2.1%)

Source: *Field Survey, 2020*

From the Table 4.5.1, it could be seen that most respondents are of not of the opinion that voting is the only way to engage in politics. From the survey, it could be seen that 47.2% agree and strongly agree cumulatively but those that that disagree amount to 35.7% and respondents that strongly disagree are 17.1%. Hence, respondents disagree with the fact that

voting is the only way to engage in politics. In order to ascertain what the respondents perceived in the course of giving their opinion about voting as the only way to engage in politics, the respondents were asked if they were of the opinion that the appropriate time to participate in politics is during elections

The table also shows that majority of the respondents believe that the appropriate time to engage in politics is during elections as 55% Agree and strongly agree to this. Likewise, 45% cumulatively disagree and strongly disagree. This shows that most respondents are not aware of political activates that exists when electioneering processes are not in play.

Table showing the perception of politics based on gender

		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Voting is enough for me to participate in politics	Strongly Agree	29	26	55
	Agree	11	11	21
	Disagree	36	27	61
	Strongly Disagree	3	0	3
	Total	79	61	140

Source: **Field survey, 2020**

From the Table 4.5.2,It could be seen that there is higher percentage among the female students who strongly agree and agree that voting process is enough to participate in politics 37(59%) of 61 of female compared to 40(50.6%) among 79 males also agree with the statement this shows that female students believed that there is no other action to perform in politics than to engage in politics furthermore it can be perceived that male students are aware of other activities involved in politics but female students perceived that voting is the only activity involved in politics.

Perception about voting

In order to ascertain the respondents' perception about voting, Item 1, 5 and 6 of Section E in the research questionnaire were directed towards ascertaining perception of voting. Furthermore, respondents were asked on their perception about voting. Item 2 of Section E quizzed respondents themselves if they don't like voting, it was seen that 35.7 agree while 14.3% strongly agree. 40.7% of the respondents disagree and 9.3 strongly disagree. Hence, we could infer from this that there is a split response as regards whether respondents love politics or not. There are evidence that there is no cut decision from the respondents if they love politics or not. We can therefore posit that respondents may or may not love politics depending on individual's perception and diverse orientation. This can be seen in Table 4.5.1

Table showing relative perception of political activities

S/N	Statement	Stronglyagree	Agree	Disagree	Stronglydisagree
1	I don't like politics	20(14.3%)	50(35.7%)	57(40.7%)	13(9.3%)
2	Voting is necessary for selecting political leaders	50(35.7%)	30(21.4%)	39(27.9%)	21(15%)
3	Voting reflects people's choice	36(25.7%)	53(37.9%)	46(32.8%)	5(3.6%)

Source: **Field survey, 2020**

From the Table, we can ascertain that majority of the respondents believe that voting is necessary for selecting political leaders as 57.1% agree and Strongly agree to this, Likewise, 52.9 cumulatively disagree and strongly disagree. This shows that the respondents are aware that electioneering process is for selecting political leaders.

Table showing cross tabulation showing the extent tribe affect political perception of students in Obafemi Awolowo University.

		Tribe			Total
		Yoruba	Igbo	Hausa	
Voting reflects people's choice	Strongly Agree	32	14	0	36
	Agree	37	15	1	53
	Disagree	32	14	0	46
	Strongly Disagree	4	1	0	5
	Total	105	44	1	140

Source: *Field Survey, 2020*

From Table 4.5.2, The Table shows that 69 out of 105 Yorubas agree and strongly agree that voting reflects the choice of the people in selecting political leader also only 29 out of the total 44 Igbos agree and strongly agree with this statement while a single respondent from Hausa tribe also agree voting reflects people's choice, 32 out of 46 that disagree about the statement comes from Yoruba tribe while the remaining 14 were from Igbo tribe also disagree however, most respondents irrespective of their tribe agree that voting reflects people's choice

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the Politicophobia and voting behavior among Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-ife.

This section begins with the discussion of findings from the demographic information of the respondents and thereafter the finding from each of the research questions which was based on politicophobia and voting behavior among Obafemi Awolowo University students.

Findings from research question 1 (What are the level political participation among Obafemi Awolowo University Students) shows that majority of the sample size attends political gathering although it's not overwhelming because quite number of respondent still don't attend political gatherings. Also taking a look at the gender effect on political participation, it could be seen that male students dominates the majority of respondents who do attends political gatherings sometimes and often, it also can be seen that the gap difference between those that attends political gatherings and those who don't attends is minima in percentage which is not helping the political institution of the society.

Findings from research question 2 (what factors are responsible for political apathy among Obafemi Awolowo University students?) shows that majority of the respondents agree that politics goes along threats which might be accompanied with threat to life in which 52.8% of the respondents agree and 47.2% disagree and this complements INEC (2015) that electoral violence has resulted in decline to the number of turnout in electoral processes

"The short-term decline between 2011 and 2015 could be attributed to the electoral violence experienced in 2011 and the failure of the government to hold to account perpetrators of the electoral violence." – INEC

Also 71.2% of the students agree that student's politicians are always suspended because of their involvement in political activities this shows that students have apartheid feeling towards political activities on campus is because of the aftermath of engaging in politics most students also sees their parents as the facilitator of their apartheid behavior to politics.

Findings from research question 3 (What is OAU undergraduate students' view about Electoral processes? Shows that most respondents disagree with the statement with that voting is the only way to engage in politics, it can be deduced that students are aware that political process is beyond voting in which 52.8% disagree with the statement that politics is the only way to engage in politics this is complements the result of research done by Adegboyega (2012) political process is beyond voting but also comprises of campaign, political meeting e.t.c.the table also shows that most respondents perception is that he appropriate time to engage in politics is during election period 55% agree this while only 45% disagree with this, even though it has been previously established that most respondents are aware of other political activities apart from voting yet, majority of the sample size believed that the most appropriate time to engage in politics is during election periods. Most male and female respondents think that voting is the only way to engage in politics although there is minimal difference between those that agree and disagree 76 and 64 respectively.

The study established that most students have various reasons for having fear of engaging in politics, suspension of their studentship is just a factor. Furthermore, majority of the students are of the view that the appropriate time to engage in politics is during election periods. The study also ascertained that variables like gender, ethnicity and religion are not relevant as

most students have similar view that voting process is enough to engage in politics. However, there is a split decision as regards respondents view about politics because most students don't like politics but strongly believe that voting and electoral processes are necessary for selecting political leaders and also most students don't engage in political activities but believe that electoral processes are necessary to reflect people's choice on political leaders.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary, conclusions and recommendations.

5.1 SUMMARY

The study examined politicophobia and voting behavior amongst Students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. The target Population is 140 Students randomly selected among the students of Obafemi Awolowo University in all 13 faculties and Post graduate college that make up the University. Questionnaire were used to collect the necessary data from respondents and meaningfully analyzed as well as interpretation of data collected.

In Chapter one, efforts were made to deliberate on the statement of the problem, objective of the study, research question, significance of the study, scope of the study and operational definition of terms was also included.

In chapter two, this project examined various works of reputable authors on politicophobia and voting behavior among Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife (OAU) students

Research methodology which comprises research design (descriptive survey), population, sample, research instrument and data analysis.

5.2 CONCLUSION

It is an indisputable fact that inspite of the fact that most students (respondents) does not love and whole heartedly participate in politics especially voting, they still believe that the only way to choose the peoples' choice leader is through voting. This is because they believe that the voting is the only way to engage in politics and also in selecting political leaders, voting process is required.

However, majority of the respondents also perceives politics to be associated with electioneering processes alone contesting, campaigns, voting etc. because that voting is enough for them to participate in politics, they are not so aware of the fact that there are other activities apart from electioneering process in politics.

In addition, majority of the students (respondents) believes that engaging in politics would lead to untimely termination of their admission because of precedent happenings like (Suspension, termination of Studentship, Extension of year of study through deliberate failing of studentsetc.) which happens to student has engage in political activities in recent years.

Based on the findings, the following conclusion was drawn: it was found that there was correlative relationship between politicophobia and voting behavior, this implies that In an attempt to eradicate fear of engaging in politics among students will bring about positive reaction towards political and thus will bring huge turnout in political activities

Finally, the result or outcome of this research substantiates that there is need for students who are youths to participate actively in politics especially in the electioneering processes for selecting political leaders in the society.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations are made:

- Both government and Academic communities should organize awareness programmes for the entire public with the aim of showing the people the reasons why their involvement in political activities especially voting is necessary and important to the development of the society and state at large.
- Tertiary institutions should encourage their students if not compulsory to engage in political activities in the institutions.
- Parents should encourage students to engage in politics in order to make them fulfill their civic right for the development of the society.
- Proper orientation about political processes should be made known to students in order to avoid electoral misconduct or the likes.

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APPENDIX

**OBAFEMI AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY
ILE-IFE.
FACULTY OF EDUCATION
DEPARTMENT OF ARTS AND SOCIAL SCIENCE EDUCATION
PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF THE CAREER PROSPECTS OF POLITICAL SCIENCE
AS A COURSE OF STUDY**

Dear respondent

A request to fill the questionnaire

The researcher is a student of Political Science, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. She is conducting research on the above topic. This questionnaire aims at eliciting relevant and substantial information regarding your perception of the career prospects of Political Science as a course of study. She humbly craves your indulgence to be unbiased in your responses to the questions posed.

There also is an assurance that the responses are basically for academic purposes, and that whatever information garnered will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thanks, in anticipation for your cooperation and responses.

SECTION A: (DEMOGRAPHIC DATA)

SEX: Male Female
AGE: 18-29 30-39 40-49 50- 59 60 and above
RELIGION: Christianity Islam Traditional Others
TRIBE: Yoruba Hausa Igbo Others

LEVEL: _____

SECTION B

Public Perception about studying Political Science

S/N	ITEM	YES	NO
1	Are you aware that Political is a professional course?		
2	Are you aware of the course known as Political Science?		
3	Have you ever met someone who studied or studying Political Science?		
4	Are you aware of the available opportunities for Political Scientists?		
5	Do you think there are career opportunities for someone who studied Political Science in Nigeria?		
6	Do you think there are career opportunities for someone who studied Political Science abroad?		
7	Do you think a Political Scientists can work all level of Government, Military, Paramilitary and Political Parties		

SECTION C

Reasons why students prefer to study Political Science or otherwise

SA - Strongly Agree, A - Agree, D - Disagree, SD - Strongly Disagree

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD
1	I love Political Science as a career or course of study				
2	I can study Political Science because I will be able to get job easily				
3	Political Scientists are respected in Nigeria				
4	Studying Political Science can make one deceptive because most Political scientists have deceptive character				
5	I can study Political Science because Political Scientists are always successful in Nigeria				
6	People study Political Science because it is lucrative				
7	I can advice young ones to study Political Science				
8	People study Political Science so that they can have access to the national cake in Nigeria				
9	One must study Political Science to be Politically relevant				

SECTION D

Societal Perception of Political Science

SA - Strongly Agree, A - Agree, D - Disagree, SD - Strongly Disagree

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD
1	Political Science is a Professional Course				
2	Political Scientists are one of the most important professional personnel in the country				
3	Political Scientist cannot be useful in any occupation than just being a politician				
4	Studying Political Science is a waste of time				
5	Those that study Political Science are governmentally relevant				
6	All Politicians serve so that they can embezzle money in				

	Nigeria				
7	People respect those that study Political Science				
8	Political Science graduates are politicians				
9	Politicians are deceptive and can't be trusted in Nigeria				
10	Political Science graduates might be treacherous because politicians are deceptive and can't be trusted in Nigeria				

SECTION E

Various interest of career available for Political Science graduates

SA - Strongly Agree, A - Agree, D - Disagree, SD - Strongly Disagree

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD
1	Political science graduates can work in any other place rather than just being a politician				
2	Political Scientists can be employed as Administrator because of their course of study				
3	Political Scientists can work with either the military or Paramilitary				
4	Political Scientists can work as a teacher/Lecturer				
5	Political Scientist can only be politician and no more				
6	Political science graduate can work in other discipline like mass media, consultant, adviser, manager e.t.c.				
7	Someone who studied Political Science ends up working as a civil servant				
8	Someone who studied Political Science ends up working as a Diplomat				
9	Someone who studied Political Science ends up working as a staff of the State and national Assemblies				

10 Where do you think a Political Scientists can work?

- (i) With Federal Government [] (ii) With State Government [] (iii) With Military []
 (iv) With Paramilitary [] (v) With Political Parties [] (vi) With Schools [] (vii) Bank [].

11 How much do you think a Political Scientists earns per month?

- (i) Less than 51,000–100,000 [] (ii) 100,000 –200,000 [] (iii) 201,000 –300,000 []
 (iv) 301,000 –400,000 [] (v) 401,000 –500,000 [] (vi) 501,000 and above []